

Ionic liquid promoted regio- and stereoselective addition of thiols to alkynes and alkenes under organic solvent free condition – A green reaction[†]

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Abstract : A simple ionic liquid, 1-methyl-3-pentylimidazolium fluoroborate, [pmIm]BF₄, promotes *anti*-Markovnikov addition of thiols to alkynes providing (*Z*)- and (*E*)-vinyl sulfides stereoselectively. The addition of thiols to alkenes in presence of another ionic liquid, [pmim]Br proceeds through *anti*-Markovnikov manner, whereas the addition to vinyl ethers and acetates occurs at more electrophilic C-2 position adjacent to oxygen. The products are obtained in high yields.

Keywords : Green chemistry, ionic liquid, thiols, alkyne, alkene.

Introduction

The addition of thiols to alkynes is of much interest in organic synthesis as the adducts, vinyl sulfides are very useful and versatile synthetic intermediates¹ being used as equivalents of enolate ions^{1b}, Michael acceptors^{1c} and in the synthesis of oxetanes^{1d}, cyclopentanones^{1e}, and cyclopentanes^{1f}. Moreover, many natural products and compounds containing vinyl sulfide moiety exhibit interesting biological properties². In the light of their synthetic utility regio- and stereoselective synthesis of 1-alkenyl sulfides from alkynes has attracted increasing attention as this is one of the most efficient and convenient methods among a variety of procedures³. The addition of thiols to alkynes can proceed under radical conditions providing the *anti*-Markovnikov products containing a mixture of (*E*)- and (*Z*)-isomers⁴. Transition metals (Mo, Pd, Pt, Rh, Ru) catalyzed additions mostly proceed in a *syn* fashion to afford *anti*-Markovnikov (*E*)-isomers or Markovnikov adducts in certain cases⁵. Recently, a cesium carbonate catalyzed addition of thiols to alkynes in presence of a radical inhibitor in DMSO provided (*Z*)-vinyl sulfides with high stereoselectivity⁶.

On the other hand, addition of thiols to alkenes is also of much importance as it provides one of the simplest routes to thioethers which are very useful building blocks for the synthesis of various organo-sulfur compounds and

they also play important roles in biological and chemical processes⁷. This reaction may also occur via an electrophilic pathway involving an ionic process or free radical conditions⁸. Usually, the free radical course promotes *anti*-Markovnikov addition, whereas ionic process leads to Markovnikov adducts⁹.

The ionic liquids have been the subject of considerable current interest in organic synthesis in the context of Green Chemistry because of their several features beneficial for environment¹⁰. We have been very actively engaged in exploring new facets of ionic liquids for useful organic transformations¹¹ and as a part of this program we report here *anti*-Markovnikov addition of thiols to alkynes and alkenes with high stereoselectivity (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

The experimental procedures for both of these reactions are very simple. For the addition of alkynes to thi-

[†]Dedicated to Professor Suresh C. Ameta on his 60th birthday.

ols, the alkyne was stirred with thiol in [pmIm]BF₄ at room temperature for a certain period of time as required (TLC). Usual work up and purification by column chromatography produced the product.

Phenyl acetylenes and substituted phenyl acetylenes underwent hydrothiolation with aromatic thiophenols and alkane thiols by this procedure under room temperature in presence of a small amount of ethanol to provide the corresponding *anti*-Markovnikov adducts as a mixture of (*E*)- and (*Z*)-isomers. Regarding stereochemistry of products the reaction of alkyne and thiophenols provided moderate to high selectivity with respect to (*E*)-isomer predominantly, while alkane thiols produced (*Z*)-isomer as major product. The results are summarized in Table 1. Possibly, this reaction is going through an ionic process

Table 1. Ionic liquid promoted addition of thiols to unactivated alkynes

$$\text{R-C}\equiv\text{C-H} \xrightarrow[\text{[pmim] BF}_4, \text{EtOH}]{\text{R}^1\text{SH}} \text{R-C}=\text{C-SR}^1$$

Entry	R	R ¹	Time (h)	Yield (%) ^a	Ratio ^b (<i>Z</i>)/(<i>E</i>)	Ref.
1	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	1.5	82	40 : 60	6
2	C ₆ H ₅	(<i>p</i> -Cl)C ₆ H ₄	2	75	10 : 90	25
3	(<i>m</i> -OMe)C ₆ H ₄	(<i>p</i> -Cl)C ₆ H ₄	3.5	75	45 : 55	
4	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	4	78	80 : 20	26
5	C ₆ H ₅	^t Bu	2.5	85	85 : 15	4a
6	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	6	10	75 : 25	6
7	(<i>p</i> -Cl)C ₆ H ₄	C ₂ H ₅	4	80	92 : 08	

^aYields refer to those of pure isolated products properly characterized by spectroscopic data.

^bThe ratio of (*Z*)/(*E*) was determined by ¹H NMR integration of corresponding peaks.

and a radical process is ruled out as it is not at all affected by the presence of a radical quencher, TEMPO (2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine oxide). Although the exact role of ionic liquid in this context is not clearly understood it is speculated that in general, ionic liquid polarizes the multiple bond (triple or double) and increases the nucleophilicity of thiol, thus facilitates the attack by thiol. The presence of ethanol in this reaction greatly improved the yields of products possibly preventing polymerization of the vinyl anion through protonation.

The addition of phenyl acetylenes with dithiol under the same experimental conditions at 70 °C produced the corresponding dithianes (Table 2). This reaction gives an easy route to dithianes, which are of much importance in organic synthesis¹².

Table 2. Ionic liquid promoted double addition of thiols to alkynes

$$\text{R-C}\equiv\text{C-H} \xrightarrow[\text{[pmim] BF}_4, \text{EtOH}]{\text{HS(CH}_2)_n\text{SH}} \text{R-C(S-CH}_2)_2\text{-H}$$

Entry	R	<i>n</i>	Time (h)	Yield (%) ^a	Ref.
1	Ph	2	6.5	70	15
2	Ph	3	6	65	16
3	(<i>p</i> -Cl)C ₆ H ₄	3	6	65	
4	(<i>m</i> -OMe)C ₆ H ₄	2	5	70	

^aThe yields refer to pure isolated products characterized by spectroscopic data.

The procedure for the addition of thiols to alkenes is also very straightforward. The mixture of alkenes and thiol in [pmIm]Br was stirred at room temperature for a required period of time (TLC). The product was obtained by direct distillation from the reaction flask under reduced pressure and in almost all the reactions the products were very pure and did not require any further purification. Significantly, the whole process does not require any organic solvent and thus it presents a green procedure. A wide range of terminal alkenes with a variety of aryl- and alkyl-substitutions underwent *anti*-Markovnikov additions to several thioalcohols to produce the corresponding thioethers by this procedure. The results are summarized in Table 3. The reaction went uniformly irrespective of nature of the substituents on the double bond. Cyclic olefins also are smoothly converted to the corresponding thioethers. Several functionalities such as Cl, Br, OMe, ethylenedioxy survived under the reaction conditions.

As expected, the addition of thiols to vinyl ethers and acetate took place at the olefinic carbon adjacent to oxygen because of its electronic influence. The results were reported in Table 4.

In general, the reactions are fast, clean and high yielding. In absence of ionic liquid no reaction was initiated.

Table 3. Ionic liquid promoted addition of thiols to alkenes

Entry	R	R ¹	R ²	Time (h)	Yield (%) ^a	Ref.
1		Me	C ₆ H ₅	0.75	90	8b
2		H	C ₂ H ₅	1.0	82	21
3		H	(<i>p</i> -Cl)C ₆ H ₄	0.75	92	8b
4		H	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	1.0	80	8b
5		H	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	0.8	85	18
6		H	(<i>p</i> -Cl)C ₆ H ₄	0.75	93	8b
7		H	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	1.0	84	18
8		H	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	1.0	78	8b
9		H	C ₆ H ₅	0.60	94	8b
10		H	C ₆ H ₅	1.5	73	8b
11		H	C ₆ H ₅	0.75	90	8b
12		H	(<i>p</i> -Cl)C ₆ H ₄	0.8	93	8b
13			C ₆ H ₅	3.0 ^b	74	21
14			C ₂ H ₅	3.5 ^b	65	20
15			C ₂ H ₅	3.5 ^b	63	21
16	<i>n</i> -Hexyl	H	C ₂ H ₅	3.0 ^b	75	21
17	<i>n</i> -Hexyl	H	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	3.5 ^b	72	17
18	<i>n</i> -Hexyl	H	C ₂ H ₅	3.5 ^b	68	19

^aThe yields refer to pure isolated products characterized by IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopic data.

^bThe reaction was carried out at 60 °C.

No organic solvent or conventional catalyst is also required for the reactions. The ionic liquid was recycled for 3 runs without any loss of efficiency. The products from alkyne addition reactions were obtained sufficiently pure (>95%) just after work up and purification through

a short column chromatography provided analytically pure compound. The stereochemistry of the alkyne-adducts (Table 1) were determined from the chemical shifts and coupling constants of the corresponding protons in their ¹H NMR spectra.

Table 4. Addition of thiols to electron deficient alkenes

Entry	Substrate	Thiol	Product	Time (h)	Yield (%) ^a	Ref.
1		0.75	84	22		
2		0.75	80	8b		
3		1.0	76	14		
4		0.75	82	8b		
5		1.0	80	23		
6		0.75	88	24		

^aThe yields refer to pure isolated products characterized by IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopic data.

Conclusion :

The present procedure using simple and inexpensive ionic liquids for the regio- and stereoselective addition of thiols to alkynes and alkenes provides a novel route to the synthesis of (*E*)- and (*Z*)-vinyl sulfides, dithianes and thioethers. This methodology offers marked improvements with regard to operational simplicity, excellent regio- (*anti*-Markovnikov) and stereoselectivity, room temperature and milder reaction conditions, considerably fast reaction, high isolated yields of products and green reaction using no organic solvent. Thus, this further demonstrates the potential of ionic liquids as efficient promoters for organic reactions.

Experimental

General : NMR spectra were recorded with a DPX-300 instrument at 300 MHz for ¹H and at 75 MHz for ¹³C. IR spectra were measured with a FT 8300 Shimadzu spectrometer. The alkenes, alkynes and thiols are mostly commercial materials and were distilled before use. A few alkynes and alkenes were prepared using standard procedures. The ionic liquid, [pmIm]Br was prepared using reported¹³ procedures.

General procedure for the anti-Markovnikov addition of thiols to alkynes : (a) *Preparation of phenyl-vinyl phenyl sulfide (entry 1, Table 1)* : A mixture of phenyl acetylene (102 mg, 1 mmol) in dry ethanol (2.5 mL) and thiophenol (110 mg, 1 mmol) in ionic liquid, [pmIm]BF₄ (250 mg) was stirred at room temperature for 1.5 h (TLC). The reaction mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate

(3 × 5 mL) and the combined extract was washed successively with water, aqueous (10%) NaOH solution, water, brine and dried over Na₂SO₄. Evaporation of solvent left the crude product which was purified by short column chromatography over silica gel (hexane-ethyl acetate : 99 : 1) to furnish pure product phenyl-vinyl phenyl sulfide as a pale yellow liquid (173 mg, 82%) as a pure (*E*)- and (*Z*)-isomer. The known compounds were identified by comparison of their spectral data with those reported (Table 1), and the new compounds were properly characterized by their IR, ¹H NMR, and ¹³C NMR spectroscopic data and elemental analysis. The ionic liquid remaining in the flask was washed with small amount of ethyl acetate and dried under vacuum at 80 °C and was reused for 3 runs without any loss of efficiency.

4-Chlorophenyl 3-methoxyphenylvinyl sulfide (as a mixture of Z/E- isomers, entry 3 in Table 1) : IR (neat) : ν 2970, 2926, 1593, 1555, 1415 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 3.77 (3H, s, *Z*-isomer), 3.82 (3H, s, *E*-isomer), 6.40 (1H, d, *J* 10.7 Hz, *Z*), 6.57 (1H, d, *J* 10.7 Hz, *Z*), 6.68 (1H, d, *J* 15.3 Hz, *E*), 6.78–6.86 (4H, m), 6.91–6.93 (1H, m), 7.06–7.08 (2H, m), 7.13–7.38 (10H, m) ppm; ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) : δ 55.1, 55.2, 111.3, 113.1, 113.3, 113.8, 118.6, 121.3, 122.9, 125.5, 127.7, 129.2 (2C), 129.3 (2C), 129.4, 129.6, 131.0 (2C), 131.2 (2C), 132.3, 132.9, 133.2, 133.6, 134.6, 137.4, 137.6, 159.4, 159.8 ppm (2 sets for each isomer). C₁₅H₁₃ClO (276.78) : Calcd. C, 65.09; H, 4.73; Found C, 64.90; H, 4.70.

(*Z*)-(4-Chlorophenyl)vinyl ethyl sulfide (entry 7,

Table 1 : IR (neat) : ν 2970, 2926, 1595, 1560, 1488, 1400, 1265, 1090, 1010, 829 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 1.35 (3H, t, J 7.4 Hz), 2.82 (2H, q, J 7.4 Hz), 6.28 (1H, J 10.9 Hz), 6.39 (1H, J 10.9 Hz), 7.31 (2H, d, J 10.9 Hz), 7.41 (2H, d, J 10.9 Hz) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 15.3, 29.6, 124.1, 127.9, 128.2 (2C), 129.7 (2C), 131.9, 135.4 ppm; $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClS}$ (198.71) : Calcd. C, 60.44; H, 5.58; Found C, 60.33; H, 5.61.

The bis-additions of thiols to alkynes were also achieved following the same experimental procedure as for reactions in Table 1 at 70 °C using 2 equivalents of dithiol for 1 equivalent of alkyne. The products except in entries 3, 4 (Table 2) are known and were identified by comparison of their NMR (^1H and ^{13}C) spectra with those reported (ref. in Table 2). The spectroscopic data (IR, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR) and elemental analysis of the compounds that have not been reported in the literature are provided below :

2-(4-Chloro-benzyl)-[1,3]dithiane (entry 3, Table 2) : IR (neat) : ν 2968, 2925, 2870, 1490, 1448, 1406, 1263, 1093, 1014 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 1.74–1.82 (2H, m), 2.70–2.82 (4H, m), 2.91 (2H, d, J 7.2 Hz), 4.12 (1H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 7.12 (2H, d, J 9.5 Hz), 7.20 (2H, d, J 9.5 Hz) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 25.5, 30.4 (2C), 40.9, 48.3, 128.3 (2C), 130.4 (2C), 132.5, 135.6 ppm; $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClS}_2$ (244.80) : Calcd. C, 53.97; H, 5.35; Found : C, 53.01; H, 5.01.

2-(3-Methoxy-benzyl)-[1,3]dithiolene (entry 4, Table 2) : IR (neat) : ν 2999, 2922, 2833, 1598, 1583, 1488, 1463, 1317, 1259, 1153, 1049 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 3.01 (2H, d, J 7.2 Hz), 3.07–3.34 (4H, m), 3.79 (3H, s), 4.72 (1H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 6.73–6.87 (3H, m), 7.19–7.24 (1H, m) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 75 MHz) : δ 38.4 (2C), 45.1, 54.6, 55.1, 112.0, 114.0, 121.2, 129.2, 140.5, 159.4; $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{14}\text{OS}_2$ (226.36) : Calcd. C, 58.37; H, 6.23; Found : C, 58.02; H, 6.11.

General procedure for the addition of thiols to alkynes : Preparation of 1-(1-methyl-2-phenylsulfanyl-ethyl)-benzene (entry 1, Table 3) : A mixture of α -methyl styrene (590 mg, 5 mmol) and thiophenol (550 mg, 5 mmol) was stirred at room temperature in ionic liquid, [pmIm]Br (250 mg) until completion of reaction (TLC). The pure product (1.02 g, 90%) was isolated by direct distillation from the reaction mixture under reduced pressure. The compound was identified by comparison of its spectra

(IR, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR) with those reported^{8b}. The remaining ionic liquid was washed with EtOAc and dried in vacuum at 80 °C for 4–5 h and reused up to 2 times without any appreciable loss of catalytic efficiency. After 2 times 50% of fresh ionic liquid was added for subsequent runs.

This procedure was followed for all reactions listed in Table 3 and Table 4. All the products are known and were easily identified by comparison of their IR, NMR (^1H and ^{13}C) spectra with those reported (ref. in Tables 3, 4).

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